

Research Software Engineering in the Age of Generative AI: Building a Community Vision

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Executive Summary

The [Research Software Engineering in the Age of Generative AI: Building a Community Vision](#) workshop, held in March in Edinburgh, UK, brought together participants to explore how Generative AI may reshape the research software ecosystem, and to help inform a broader community vision for the future of the field.

Before the workshop, attendees contributed to a draft vision statement that workshop organisers used to identify areas of agreement and difference. A version of this, published as [Research Software in an Age of AI-Assisted Development: Reflections from Edinburgh](#), is intended to provide principles that will guide the community during this time of rapid change. In the workshop, the participants also discussed emerging practices, identified opportunities and risks, and proposed a range of high-impact pilot activities to support the safe, reproducible, and effective use of AI in research software and workflows. The areas focused on included:

1. Suggesting policies and narratives for research-performing institutions
2. Developing a framework to discover, document and address costs, benefits, and risks
3. Understanding future incentives around publishing, preserving and crediting software
4. Verifying and validating research software
5. Defining pathways for the evolution of the research software engineers (RSE) role
6. Identifying and developing necessary training
7. Developing a playbook for RSE managers and open-source software project leaders
8. Making GenAI accessible to all
9. Collaborating together across people, community, and disciplines, not just with AI

Across these areas, participants identified 46 different activities, ranging from writing sprints and community-of-practice activities that could begin soon, to longer-term research studies to investigate how verification practices, collaboration patterns, and training needs are changing as AI tools become embedded in research workflows. These projects shared a common focus on community-maintained practices, actionable guidance, and sustained coordination.

Information on these possible projects will now be widely disseminated. If you're interested in supporting and/or being involved in any of these projects then contact Michelle Barker, michelle@researchsoft.org and/or Arfon Smith, arfon@schmidtsciences.org.

The Research Software Alliance (ReSA) was supported to undertake this work as part of [Schmidt Sciences](#) grant G-25-69965, with local support from the Software Sustainability Institute (SSI).

1. Introduction

The [Research Software Engineering in the Age of Generative AI: Building a Community Vision](#) workshop, held in March in Edinburgh, UK, brought together participants to explore how Generative AI may reshape the research software ecosystem, and to help inform a broader community vision for the future of the field.

Participants discussed emerging practices, identified opportunities and risks, and proposed a range of high-impact pilot activities to support the safe, reproducible, and effective use of AI in research software and workflows. This report provides details of the workshop rationale, aims and organisation, outputs and next steps.

2. Background

Research software engineering is essential across all computational research disciplines. GenAI has the potential to accelerate this work (e.g., faster prototyping, automation, and broader access), but also poses significant risks (reliability and correctness, comprehension debt, provenance gaps, reproducibility debt, security, and bias). In the coming years, the growing use of Generative AI will change who develops research software and how it is produced, but the need for trustworthy, well-maintained software, as well as the people/experts who assure these qualities, will remain critical. Shared guardrails and practices are needed to harness the gains and manage the risks of GenAI.

The research software (and broader open source software) community is grappling with both the opportunities and challenges that are arising, with relevant resources (published before the workshop was conducted) including:

- The [Position Statement on Generative AI in the RSE Workplace](#) on how GenAI is impacting research software engineers (RSEs), and the vision RSEs have for their profession in this new technological landscape. This work was co-led by the [Alliance for Data Science and AI](#) (ADSA) and [United States Research Software Engineering Association](#) (US-RSE) in late 2025.
- The [Report of the 2025 Workshop on Next-Generation Ecosystems for Scientific Computing: Harnessing Community, Software, and AI for Cross-Disciplinary Team Science](#) by Lois Curfman McInnes et al. summarises insights from a gathering of over 40 experts, outlining a path toward more powerful, sustainable, and collaborative scientific software ecosystems.
- [RSEs 2035: Surviving or Thriving in the Age of AI](#) by Sandra Gesing concludes that the survival of RSEs requires intentional action, including recognizing software as scholarship, investing in workforce development, and proactively addressing the policy implications of AI in research.

- [Future Challenges for RSE](#) by Florian Goth et al. shares how participants of the deRSE25 conference imagined a future where RSEs have a well-defined and well-integrated role.
- [Threats to scientific software from over-reliance on AI code assistants](#) by Gabrielle O'Brien outlines the factors that place scientific code at risk and suggests directions for research groups, educators, publishers and funders to counter these liabilities.

A range of conversations were also already occurring around this, such as:

- [Beyond Code: Engineering Trustworthy Software Systems with AI at Scale](#), a workshop to develop a research agenda that articulates a roadmap for the evolving role of AI in developing complex software systems. This workshop in February 2026 was co-sponsored by the Computing Research Association (CRA) and IEEE Computer Society (CS).
- [Research Software Engineering in the Age of AI](#), a [panel](#) to discuss AI's impact in the context of HPC and research software engineering: development and maintenance of the software used in scientific computing and research. This workshop occurred at the [SC25 conference](#) in November 2025.

However, while valuable discussions and research were already underway across this area — often with different focal points and involving different stakeholder groups — there remained a gap in broader community-wide discussion and coordination regarding possible ways forward.

3. Workshop aims and organisation

This 2.5-day workshop aimed to bring together ~35 leaders in research software and AI to explore how Generative AI may reshape the research software ecosystem, and to help inform a broader community vision for the future of the field. Generative AI is significantly affecting those who develop and maintain research software, and the workshop aimed to consider these effects.

The workshop aimed to enable sharing of practices and experiences, examination of key levers of change in a range of communities, and identify opportunities for collective learning, coordination, and future collaboration. To support this, a range of optional activities occurred before the workshop to maximise the range of inputs used in planning. These included:

1. Survey of attendees on topics relating to the future of research software personnel, what types of interventions are needed, what's already happening, and local challenges.
2. Public survey with 23 responses
3. Submission of lightning talks by attendees
 - a. Beyond the Library: Research Software Engineering in the Age of Zero-Cost Code by Yael Elmatad - [slides](#)
 - b. Deciding when GenAI is the right tool for the job by Sue Smith - [slides](#)

- c. Evaluation of Kilo code with AI orientated development workflows by Kamilla Kopec-Harding - [slides](#)
 - d. Gen AI in Research Software Production by Vani Mandava - [slides](#)
 - e. How Scientists are Programming with GenAI by Elle O'Brien - [slides](#)
 - f. Research Software, AI and Metascience by Joseph Shingleton - [slides](#)
 - g. Situated knowledge and the use of generative AI in research software engineering by Yo Yehudi (and Laura Carter) - [slides](#)
4. Submission of position papers by attendees
 5. The workshop organizers created a draft vision statement which workshop attendees and some additional community members contributed to the document in advance of the workshop, including refining the document, adding disagreements, and identifying gaps. Based on this, the organizers refined the document to include principles, benefits, challenges, and open questions, as inputs for the in-person elements of the workshop.
 6. Inputs by attendees to a list of [resources](#)

We are grateful for the 23 responses to the public survey questions on:

- a. What will happen with research software engineers? Will current RSE positions disappear, evolve (e.g., toward training, oversight, infrastructure), or take some other form? What will today's RSEs be doing in five years?
- b. What about new RSEs? Will they still be hired? If so, will their role differ from more experienced RSEs? Where will they come from?
- c. What about new RSEs? Will they still be hired? If so, will their role differ from more experienced RSEs? Where will they come from?
- d. What's needed to get there? Beyond current efforts, what's missing? Do we need new experiments, tools, training, policies, something else? Feel free to provide multiple answers, or answers that have multiple, possibly-dependent aspects.
- e. What's already happening? What are you or others doing now to move toward this future?
- f. What concerns you? Are there risks we're not discussing? For example, challenges around equity, access, institutional divides, something else?

These were similar to the attendee surveys responses, with major themes including:

- GenAI is a major disrupter but RSEs will evolve rather than disappear.
- Workforce adaptation is needed, and quickly
- Inequality and institutional divides may increase
- Quality, reproducibility, and trust are key issues

There was some different emphasis on these points, with attendees feeling slightly more positive about the continued need for RSEs than the public respondents. Attendees also focused a little more on ecosystem change (including institutional structures, governance and policy), which likely reflected their often senior status, although many were also concerned with

practical solutions. In contrast, public responses overall reflected a more pragmatic and operational approach.

These inputs were used to shape the final agenda, which included scene-setting, lightning talks and multiple rounds of focused working groups, to enable participants to focus on:

- Advancing safe, reproducible, and effective use of GenAI across research software and workflows in universities and research institutes.
- Diagnosing current gaps (training, experimentation capacity, governance, reproducibility, and “new ways of working”)
- Defining a vision for how RSE work will evolve with GenAI and how teams will adapt new collaboration models – regardless of job title – and how teams organize to deliver quality research software.
- Identifying how to state expertise and share information on the opportunities and risks GenAI creates for research (through a software engineering lens), targeted to specific audiences (funders, universities, labs/institutes, PIs, and RSE leaders).

The 37 workshop participants (see Appendix 1) were selected to represent a cross-section of early adopters, supporters and constructive critics of innovative AI tooling in research organisations. This representation was not exhaustive, and this was acknowledged and explored during the workshop.

Image: Workshop participants

The workshop was co-led by Schmidt Sciences and the Research Software Alliance (ReSA), with local support provided by the Software Sustainability Institute (SSI).

ReSA is an international organisation that unites decision-makers and key influencers across the international research and innovation community. Some of ReSA's recent outcomes which enhance access to and discoverability of research software includes a [position paper](#) on the criticality of research software to AI-driven research, in collaboration with the [Digital Research Alliance of Canada](#).

ReSA fills a crucial niche, creating much-needed opportunities for decision-makers across the entire research software community to come together to discover solutions, learn best practices, and share the knowledge that advances progress. Major international initiatives led by ReSA that have created principles and guidelines for different stakeholders include:

- Co-leading the development of the [FAIR for Research Software Principles](#), including a 2-year review and [adoption update](#).
- [Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability](#) (ADORE.software), an outcome of the ReSA-led [Research Software Funders Forum](#) and its annual hybrid events, which engage more than 60 funders globally.
- Co-leading the [Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software \(PRO4RS\) Working Group](#) to improve support and recognition by research institutions.

SSI helps people build better and more sustainable software to enable world-class research. Since 2010, the SSI has played a vital role in the UK and worldwide in advancing research culture, supporting future research software leaders, revolutionising access to software training and working with collaborators to develop policies that better recognise and support software in research.

4. Workshop outputs

The main outputs of the workshop are:

- [Research Software in an Age of AI-Assisted Development: Reflections from Edinburgh](#), a snapshot of attendee discussion before the workshop that captures a sense of the identified principles, benefits, challenges, and open questions.
- A set of possible projects to advance safe, reproducible, and effective use of Generative AI in research software and workflows (i.e., this report).
- An informal [list of resources](#) covering the following areas:
 - Skills and training
 - Careers and incentives
 - Tools and infrastructure
 - Governance, policy and safety
 - Community and culture
 - Evaluation and metrics

To create the list of possible projects, participants discussed emerging practices, identified opportunities and risks, and proposed a range of high-impact project activities to support the safe, reproducible, and effective use of AI in research software and workflows. The areas focused on included:

1. Suggesting policies and narratives for research-performing institutions
2. Developing a framework to discover, document and address costs, benefits, and risks
3. Understanding future incentives around publishing, preserving and crediting software
4. Verifying and validating research software
5. Defining pathways for the evolution of the RSE role
6. Identifying and developing necessary training
7. Developing a playbook for RSE managers and open-source software project leaders
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Across these areas, participants identified and prioritized 46 different projects, ranging from writing sprints and community-of-practice activities that could begin soon, to longer-term research studies to investigate how verification practices, collaboration patterns, and training needs are changing as AI tools become embedded in research workflows. These projects shared a common focus on community-maintained practices, actionable guidance, and sustained coordination.

A list of all the projects is included in Appendix 2. A high-level summary of all the projects is also provided in the table below.

Name	Type	Size (Small, Med, Large)	Readiness
1A: Talking point memo generation to support RSEs	Pilot	M-L	High
1B: How to get institutions to offer the appropriate tools needed for research software	Study	M-L	Medium
1C: Whether RSE work/impact/role actually changes with GenAI emergence	Study	L	High
2A: Writing sprint to create a tradeoffs framework relevant to understanding AI risks	Pilot	S	High
2B: Extension of responsible AI risk register using the tradeoffs framework	Pilot	S	High
2C: Create public website around the responsible AI risk register and tradeoffs framework	Pilot	M	Medium
2D: How to use the tradeoffs framework in different	Training	M	Medium

scenarios			
2E: How to contribute to the tradeoffs framework	Training	S	Medium
2F: Evaluate usage of the framework training (2D) materials	Study	L	Medium
3A: Identify what existing attribution frameworks should be reviewed for updates related to AI usage	Pilot	L	High
3B: Case study on 3-5 recent computational research publications and how attribution artifacts have changed/could change	Pilot	M	Medium
3C: Study - how does our ability to use GenAI affect reproducibility?	Pilot	L	Low-medium
4A: Verification and validation skills for LLM coding agents in research software	Pilot	S-M	High
4B: Spec-driven development as a verification substrate for AI-assisted research software	Pilot	M	Medium-high
4C: Cross-programme synthesis of AI-assisted RSE practice	Pilot	S	High
4D: Voices of Scientific Testers – an ethnographic study of changing review practice in scientific OSS	Pilot	M	Medium
4E: Theory-to-code translation in the GenAI era	Pilot	M	Medium
4F: Empirical study: how should V&V practice vary with research software type?	Pilot	M-L	Medium
4G: Verification and validation of scientific software that contains AI components at runtime	Pilot	L	Low-medium
4H: Behavioural verification methods for research software pipelines	Pilot	M-L	Medium
5A: Visual aid to describe changing role of RSE in the context of GenAI	Pilot	S	In progress - see blog post
5B: Propose/Organize workshop(s) that brings together practitioners to share success/failures/learnings of using AI in research software	Pilot	M	High
5C: Case study of the AI practices and how they are changing for researchers, RSEs, and SEs, across industries and fields	Study	L	Low
5D: Demonstrate that RSE + AI is more effective for research software than R + AI (or SE + AI)	Study	L	Low

6A: Community of Practice for teaching research software with AI	Pilot	M	In progress
6B: Email newsletter sharing practices, studies on teaching	Pilot	S	High
6C: Qualitative meta analysis/systematic review article on current practices and assessment methods	Study	M	Medium
6D: Understand what needs to be taught for being productive in teams while adopting genAI in their workflow using existing data	Study	S	High
7A: RSE Managers' AI Adoption Playbook	Pilot	M-L	Medium-high
7B: OSS AI Adoption Playbook: guidance for open-source project leaders managing AI-era contributions	Pilot	M	Low-medium
7C: Psychologically safe AI adoption: resources for RSE managers	Training	M	Medium
7D: Upskilling materials for RSE managers: onboarding to the LLM era	Training	S-M	Medium
7E: Low-hype LLM training: peer-led workshops for RSEs on modern AI capabilities	Training	S-M	High-medium
7F: Delphi study: challenges and experiences of RSE managers navigating AI adoption	Study	M	Medium
8A: Communications plan and community management for engaging diverse targeted groups in AI in research (software/computing) discussions	Pilot	M	Low
8B: Engaging a selection of underrepresented knowledge axes through workshops, and/or through funding / incubators	Pilot	L	Low
8C: Providing playbooks for equitable AI in research advocacy	Training	L	Low
8D: Post-workshop questions on demographic of participants and who should have been here	Study	S	In progress
8#: How research software practitioners from varied knowledge axes (e.g. different domains) interface with AI policy/norms	Study	M	Low
8F: Longitudinal study identifying how LLM-using projects onboard marginalised groups	Study	L	Medium
8G: State of the Field paper on where specifically are the biases in current infrastructure in research software	Study	L	Medium

9A: AI-assisted requirements gathering ("PRD skill") for research software collaborations	Pilot	M	Medium
9B: Cross-domain translation tool for RSE "cold starts"	Pilot	S-M	High
9C: AI-drafted decision and assumption logs for research software projects	Pilot	M	Medium
9D: SPACE-framework study of research teams adopting AI collaboration tools	Study	M-L	Medium
9E: Empirical study: does AI mediation change the epistemic quality of research collaborations?	Study	L	Low-medium

5. Next steps

This report, the related "[Research Software in an Age of AI-Assisted Development: Reflections from Edinburgh](#)" document (developed before the workshop as a vision document), and information on these possible projects will be widely disseminated by the workshop organisers, including to relevant research software decision makers and influencers via the ReSA forums for [funders](#), [publishers](#), [policymakers](#), [skills and training](#), [metascience](#), [community leadership](#), [infrastructure](#), and the [International Council of RSE Associations](#).

Submissions are also being proposed to share the workshop content and outputs at a range of community events in 2026, including:

- [Trillian Parameter Consortium \(TPC\) 26](#), Baltimore, USA, May 31 – June 3, 2026
- [International Research Software Conference \(IRSC26\)](#), Sheffield, UK (with remote attendance available), 7-8 September, 2026
- [RSECon26](#), Sheffield, UK (with remote attendance available), 9-11 September, 2026
- [USRSE'26](#), San Jose, USA, 19-21 October, 2026
- [Research Software Asia Australia Conference](#) (RSAA26), online, 25-28 August, 2026

If you're interested in supporting and/or being involved in any of the possible projects then contact Michelle Barker, michelle@researchsoft.org. To stay up to date on opportunities to engage further, longer-term outcomes of the workshop, and other items of interest to the research software community, subscribe to the [ReSA newsletter](#).

Appendix 1: List of participants

In alphabetical order:

1. Samantha Ahern – University College London / Society of RSE / The Carpentries
2. Michelle Barker – Research Software Alliance [Organiser]
3. Neil Chue Hong – University of Edinburgh / Software Sustainability Institute
4. Ian Cosden – Princeton University
5. Tina Dang – Schmidt Sciences
6. Ryan Daniels – Accelerate Programme for Scientific Discovery, University of Cambridge
7. Stephan Druskat – German Aerospace Center (DLR)
8. Anshu Dubey – Argonne National Laboratory
9. Yael Elmatad – Open Athena
10. Cunliang Geng – Netherlands eScience Center
11. Sandra Gesing – US Research Software Engineer Association
12. Josh Greenberg – Alfred P. Sloan Foundation
13. Robert Haines – University of Manchester
14. Kim Hartley – Research Software Alliance [Organiser]
15. James Hetherington – University College London (UCL), Advanced Research Computing (ARC)
16. Toby Hodges – The Carpentries
17. James Howison – University of Texas at Austin
18. Daniel S. Katz – University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign [Organiser]
19. Kamilla Kopec-Harding – University of Birmingham
20. Richard Littauer – CURIOS
21. Christina Maimone – Northwestern University
22. Vani Mandava – University of Washington, Scientific Software Engineering Center (SSEC)
23. Rohan Marwaha – National Center for Supercomputing Applications (NCSA)
24. Elle O'Brien – University of Michigan
25. Adrian Price-Whelan – Simons Foundation
26. Karthik Ram – University of California, Berkeley
27. Joseph Shingleton – University of Glasgow
28. Arfon Smith – Schmidt Sciences [Organiser]
29. Sue Smith – Independent
30. Nathan TeBlunthuis – University of Texas at Austin
31. Anelda Van der Walt – Talarify/University of Cape Town, South Africa
32. Steve Van Tuyl – Alliance for Data Science and AI
33. Ben van Werkhoven – Leiden University
34. Kirstie Whitaker – Berkeley Institute for Data Science
35. Greg Wilson – Independent
36. Sherry Wu – Carnegie Mellon University
37. Yo Yehudi – Open Life Science (OLS)

Appendix 2: List of possible projects from each working group (WG)

WG1: Policy and Narrative Suggestions for Institutions

1.1 Pilots

1A: Talking point memo generation to support RSEs

- A new core argument for RSEs - to be developed by a working group
- Series of very targeted PR/marketing themes (short, bullets + supporting evidence where it exists) for specific audiences made public for reuse and localization. 1 paragraph, 1 page, 3 page, 5 page version.
- Need initial deliverables, with feedback and then revision and updates
- Key audiences: institutional leadership, funders, governments, PIs/domain scientists, frontier ai labs, industry affiliates
- For each audience, think about variance within the audience in terms of AI posture and predisposition to/knowledge of RSE and their primary goals

Size of task: Medium-large

- Need a quick initial draft output that's a smaller effort

Readiness: High

Timeline: Needs to happen and complete soon to have impact

Key stakeholders: Who needs to contribute - PIs, RSE leaders and RSEs, community

Venues / opportunities:

Deliverables:

- Bullet point lists
- Personas
- Case studies - success stories, learnings based on actual examples
- Diagrams
- One-pagers
- This group is not doing studies - may inform what type of evidence is needed or would be persuasive, should disseminate study results and evidence
- How to accomplish this:
 - Working group meeting at least biweekly (every 2 weeks)
 - Propose sessions at conferences to share the output and get input - workshops or BoFs?

Impact: Create policy, inform strategic direction, incorporate RSE in bigger institutional AI plans and funding trajectories from various sources - gov, philanthropy, etc

- Challenges/need for funding: how to get the time from people needed to do this – paid time out of their day jobs, or pay someone to do it on behalf of the societies. This will not happen due to human capacity reasons without being able to pay for dedicated time.
-

1.2 Studies

1B: How to get institutions to offer the appropriate GenAI tools needed for research software

- That is, how can we use something besides Microsoft Copilot and still have institutional compliance?
- What are researchers actually using to create software - what do they need?
- What are institutional concerns leading to tool restriction?
- What are the risks to research progress of not having access to leading tools?
- What are the real security risks? Go beyond reactive hype about security and define risks for institutions and research in more detail
- Can use the international 2026 RSE survey results, also need other data

Size of task: Medium

Readiness: Medium

Key stakeholders: People who make institutional tool choices, RSEs, PIs/domain researchers, IT, institutional security office

Deliverables: Report on what is happening and based on observed practice and studies and produce a series of recommendations for institutions

Impact: Influence institutional policy and practices re: tool procurement

Challenges: Tools are changing rapidly, institutions reluctant to commit to things when there isn't agreement within institution on what tools,

1C: Whether RSE work/impact/role actually changes with GenAI emergence

- Also the impacts on the teams during those changes

Size of task: Large

Readiness: High

- Ready to move forward now; There is a start on an [RSE job description collection in US](#), international RSE study has been run with questions, Sloan ethnographic study, ReSA metascience ideas on forecasting changes to RSE workforce with UK case study (Delphi

study+SWOT analysis). There is also the International RSE Survey that has questions on use and adoption.

Key stakeholders: International Council of RSE Associations,

Venues / opportunities: Report or series of publications - RSE conferences, journals, open access monograph?

Impact: Government, HEI and funder policy

Note: This project does not necessarily fit under the communications topic, but has implications for policy. Could feed into future narratives.

WG2: Tradeoffs Framework (Costs, Benefits, Risks)

2.1. Pilots

2A: Writing sprint to create a tradeoffs framework relevant to understanding AI risks

- To create an initial version of a framework

Size of task: Small

Readiness: High

- Ready to go (consult with Turing Way about best number of participants)

Key stakeholders: Some of the working group members from the workshop are interested.

Venues / opportunities: Virtual or any place where the right people can come

2B: Extension of Responsible AI Risk Register using the tradeoffs framework

- One feedback cycle will come from the community at the SSI Collaborations Workshop

Size of task: Small

Readiness: High

- A version could be done now; and more when 2A is completed

Key stakeholders: Small number of people to help Joseph Shingleton test the workshop, then enough suitable people to participate in the workshop

Venues / opportunities: Collaborations Workshop, could rerun at RSECon26 as a further pilot

2C: Create public website around the responsible AI risk register and tradeoffs framework

Ensure website is a citable object

Run community webinar about framework

Revise framework / add vignettes based on this

Ensure framework is a citable object

Size of task: Medium

Readiness: Medium

- Requires Pilot 2B, would benefit from the guidance that the training project (2D) will produce

Key stakeholders:

- RSEs
- Group Leaders
- Funders
- Policymakers

Venues / opportunities:

- Publish a public, citable version with a DOI
 - Launch at somewhere like RSECon / US-RSE Annual conference / for the RSEs
 - Introduction to policymakers at a suitable venue? OECD, UNESCO, UN Open Source
-

2.2. Training

2D: How to use the tradeoffs framework in different scenarios

- First part is to create different guidance as part of the training materials
- Scenarios include:
 - An RSE (or a software project leader / team) deciding what, how, why to use AI for a project
 - An RSE group (leader and team) discussing the use of AI in their group
 - Funders of research software
 - To help provide guidance to applicants on how to talk about how and why they're using AI in their proposed projects

Size of task: Medium

Readiness: Medium

- Requires Pilot 2A

Key stakeholders: RSEs, RSE leaders, funders

Venues / opportunities:

2E: How to contribute to the tradeoffs framework

- Particularly e.g. additional vignettes and example risks / benefits / costs

First part is to create guidance as part of the training materials

Size of task: Small

Readiness: Medium

- No dependencies, though benefits from Pilot 2A and Training 2D being completed

Key stakeholders: The prioritized

Venues / opportunities:

2.3 Studies

2F: Evaluate usage of the framework training (2D) materials

- Provide access to materials to users to gain feedback and evaluate usage.
- Validation of whether the taxonomy is “complete”
- Validation that the use of this type of taxonomy is useful to enable discourse in this area
- Validating that the training material accompanying the framework

Size of task: Large

Readiness: Depends on 2A, 2C, 2D, 2F

Key stakeholders: RSE and non-RSE researchers, RSE leaders, funders, people with UI/UX expertise

Venues / opportunities:

WG3: Incentives for Publishing, Preserving and Crediting Code

3.1 Pilots

3A: Identify what existing attribution frameworks should be reviewed for updates related to AI usage

- Gather a focus group of attribution framework projects (e.g. related to sharing & publication research software, to prototype changes that include AI artifacts and traces (e.g., skills), to data models, schemas, workflows, etc. (Perhaps in a ReSA Research Software Infrastructure forum meeting?)
 - Examples include:
 - [Citation File Format](#) - Add metadata fields?
 - [CodeMeta](#) - “
 - [InvenioRDM](#) - “ (and more?)
 - pURL - for skills? (thus linking into the SBOM world)
 - [Skills.sh](#)
 - Leverage existing and emerging security frameworks and tools for screening skills - e.g. <https://www.ripple tide.com/dev>
 - Additional metadata should be shared: plans / specs used in AI-driven implementation(skillsmeta, plansmeta, specsmeta).
- Output: Make recommendations to attribution infrastructure projects, groups, or communities

Size of task: Large

- Depending on the scope and number of communities/projects engaged, the size could be smaller

Readiness: High

- This could start immediately with a working group focused on identifying critical, RSE-related attribution frameworks that ought to be reviewed for AI updates

Key stakeholders:

- Members of communities/projects that could be impacted by the need for framework updates
- ReSA Research Software Infrastructure Forum
- Working groups, task forces, etc. from regional RSE organizations

Venues / opportunities:

- Virtual working group
- Possibility to meet in-person at existing RSE focused conferences

3B: Case study on 3-5 recent computational research publications and how attribution artifacts have changed/could change

- Identify a handful of recent computational research publications that have good attribution in place (code citation and sharing best practices, etc.)
- Re-analyze the outputs of these studies through an AI-lens - how should attribution practices change if AI was incorporated into the development of code and other research artifacts

Size of task: Medium

- The project could be carried out by a small group over a fairly short period of time (4-6 months of low-effort?)

Readiness: Medium

- Requires finding a dedicated group to take on the tasks
- Possibly should follow the above project (“Identify what existing attribution frameworks should be reviewed...”) or iterate with it

Key stakeholders: Authors of selected papers

Venues / opportunities: This work is publishable and presentable at RSE focused venues and possibly in domain focused venues

3C: How does our ability to use GenAI affect reproducibility?

- Identify one or more reproducibility studies to re-visit with GenAI as an assistant
- Questions asked:
 - Does using GenAI to assist with replication affect the reproducibility of a study?
 - Example: [revisit the PSYCHOLOGY study using GenAI](#)

Size of task: Large

Readiness: Low-medium

- Requires a dedicated team to conduct the study

Key stakeholders:

- Original authors
- Domain of original work

Venues / opportunities: This work is publishable and presentable at RSE focused venues and in domain focused venues

WG4: Verification and Validation for Research Software

4.1 Pilots

4A: Verification and validation skills for LLM coding agents in research software

Audit the current state of SKILLS.md / CLAUDE.md / AGENTS.md files in the LLM agent ecosystem for testing and verification, and develop a research-software-specific skill (or small set of skills) that explicitly steers agents toward integration and functional testing rather than defaulting to trivial unit tests. Pilot with 2–3 research software groups already using agentic workflows; iterate based on what reviewers actually find useful.

Size of task: S–M. ~2–4 FTE-months across the audit, skill development, and a light evaluation pass.

Readiness: High. The format is already in widespread use across the agent ecosystem.

Dependencies: (1) a developer with both LLM-agent fluency and research-software experience; (2) 2–3 pilot groups doing enough AI-assisted development to exercise the skill; (3) agreed criteria for what "useful" means in the evaluation.

Key stakeholders: RSEs using AI coding agents day-to-day; maintainers of widely-used research-software libraries; the broader skills/agents ecosystem; LLM platform vendors whose agents read these files.

Venues / opportunities: Public GitHub repo as canonical home; demo/BoF at RSECon26; short methods write-up in blog posts and other community channels.

Existing commitments / momentum: The Schmidt Sciences [VISS](#) program (Arfon Smith, arfon@schmidtsciences.org, confirmed) is already partially funding adjacent agentic skills work emerging from the Edinburgh workshop, providing a natural reference point. No WG-level commitments yet confirmed.

4B: Spec-driven development as a verification substrate for AI-assisted research software

Pilot a spec-driven development workflow for AI-assisted research software, where researchers articulate the intended behaviour of a piece of code as a structured specification before the implementation is generated, and the spec then serves a dual purpose: (a) as input to the LLM to produce better-targeted code, and (b) as the artefact against which the resulting code is verified (e.g., via spec-derived tests, property checks, or behavioural comparisons). Run with 3–5 research software projects across contrasting categories (e.g. data pipeline, analysis script, simulation component) and capture both whether the workflow produces better code and whether the spec is actually useful as a verification substrate downstream. The verification

angle is the distinctive contribution: most spec-driven development work focuses on the up-front quality benefit, not the back-end V&V benefit.

Size of task: Medium. ~4–8 FTE-months across workflow development, project facilitation, and structured evaluation.

Readiness: Medium–High. Spec-driven development is already an active area inside the Schmidt Sciences VISS programme, providing both infrastructure and a candidate cohort. Dependencies: (1) coordination with VISS so this pilot complements rather than duplicates existing work; (2) 3–5 willing research projects spanning at least 2–3 software categories; (3) a shared spec template light enough that researchers will actually use it; (4) clarity up front on what "verification against the spec" concretely means for each project.

Key stakeholders: Researchers writing or commissioning AI-assisted research software; RSEs supporting them; the VISS programme team and its participating projects; the broader spec-driven-development community across industry and research; funders interested in concrete tooling outcomes.

Venues / opportunities: Embedded inside ongoing VISS engagements where appropriate; spec templates and evaluation instruments published in a public GitHub repo; early experience report read outs at RSE conference BoF sessions and practitioner venues; potential coordination with the embedded-trial work in item 3 so spec-driven projects feed into the same case-study collection.

Existing commitments / momentum: The Schmidt Sciences [VISS](#) program (Arfon Smith, arfon@schmidtsciences.org, confirmed) is an experimental initiative explicitly focused on spec-driven development and agentic workflows, providing a live testbed and existing infrastructure rather than a from-scratch effort. No individual commitments named yet.

4C: Cross-programme synthesis of AI-assisted RSE practice

Fund a small coordinator role to produce a comparable set of structured case studies and experience reports from RSE projects already underway across multiple programmes (Schmidt Sciences VISS, Netherlands eScience Center (NLeSC), Research Data Science teams (RDSci), and similar). Develop a shared template, work with project leads to capture what they tried with AI-assisted workflows and how it went, and publish the resulting collection as a public, searchable resource. The contribution is comparability across cohorts, not the case studies themselves (most of which would be written anyway), but in incompatible formats and scattered venues.

Size of task: Small. ~2–4 FTE-months for a coordinator and editorial role; participating project effort largely in-kind.

Readiness: High once the participating programmes agree to take part. Dependencies: (1) explicit buy-in from each programme on scope and template; (2) a coordinator with editorial chops and standing across the programmes involved; (3) a stable home for the collection.

Key stakeholders: Programme leads at VISS, NLeSC, RDSci, and equivalent; the project leads who would author the case studies; the broader RSE community as readership; funders interested in evidence of workflow change at programme scale.

Venues / opportunities: Public repository or community-owned collection as canonical home; lightning talk/BoF-type sessions at RSE conferences.

Existing commitments / momentum: VISS (Arfon Smith, arfon@schmidtsciences.org, confirmed), NLeSC, and RDSci are all named in the workshop notes as candidate sites with relevant work already underway. No individual commitments named yet.

4D: Voices of Scientific Testers – an ethnographic study of changing review practice in scientific OSS

Run a qualitative / ethnographic study of how code review and verification practice is changing in scientific open-source software (SOSS) projects in the LLM era. Format follows the published precedent of Organizational Mycology's "[Voices of JupyterHub](#)" and "[AstroPy community engagement](#)" reports: 15–25 in-depth interviews with leaders of major SOSS projects, plus where feasible some participant observation by a researcher with research software literacy. Output is a public report capturing how project leaders are currently feeling about and tackling these challenges, as a point-in-time grounding for the field.

Size of task: Medium. ~6–9 FTE-months across a qualitative researcher and editorial support.

Readiness: Medium. The methodology has clear precedent. Dependencies: (1) a qualitative researcher with prior work in or near research software; (2) recruitment across a representative range of scientific open source software (SOSS) projects; (3) ethics approval; (4) a publication venue committed up front.

Key stakeholders: Leaders of major SOSS projects (across domains); the wider RSE community as readership; funders supporting OSS sustainability; researchers studying open source.

Venues / opportunities: Public report following the "Voices of..." format; companion short piece in an RSE-community venue; presentation at future RSE conferences.

Existing commitments / momentum: Organizational Mycology's prior "Voices of JupyterHub" and "AstroPy community engagement" reports provide a methodological template and demonstrate that this format works for scientific OSS communities. No WG-level commitments yet confirmed.

4E: Theory-to-code translation in the GenAI era

Investigate whether GenAI makes formal (or semi-formal) mapping between scientific theory and the code that implements it easier, harder, or more important. Build on the existing literature (e.g., Jay et al., see citations below) on this question by extending it to settings where significant portions of the implementation are AI-generated. Likely a focused empirical study across 2–3 domains where the theory–code link is well-defined (e.g. mathematical physics, mathematical biology, econometrics).

Size of task: Medium. ~6–9 FTE-months for a focused study and write-up.

Readiness: Medium. Published prior art gives the study a clear starting frame and an established conceptual vocabulary. Dependencies: (1) a PI with footing in both software engineering research and at least one of the target domains; (2) recruitment of researchers in those domains willing to share artefacts; (3) agreed scope on which domains to compare.

Key stakeholders: Researchers in domains where formal theory underpins computational implementations; the established theory-software-translation research community; empirical SE researchers; the broader RSE community.

Venues / opportunities: Publication in venues that already host the prior literature (RIO Journal, F1000Research) plus an RSE-community venue; report-back at future RSE conferences; a BoF session at 2026 RSE Conferences to convene the existing community alongside new contributors.

Existing commitments / momentum: A connected pair of community workshop reports:

- Jay, C. et al. (2017). *Identifying the challenges of code/theory translation: report from the Code/Theory 2017 workshop*. *Research Ideas and Outcomes*, 3:e13236. DOI: 10.3897/rio.3.e13236
- Jay, C. et al. (2020). *The challenges of theory-software translation*. *F1000Research*, 9:1192. DOI: 10.12688/f1000research.25561.1

These establish "theory-software translation" as a defined research area with a known author group spanning the UK and US. Several authors of these papers remain active in the RSE research community.

4F: Empirical study: how should V&V practice vary with research software type?

Empirically investigate how appropriate V&V practice varies across research software categories in an LLM-assisted development context. Working from an existing taxonomy (e.g.

Hasselbring et al. 2024), select 4–6 contrasting categories (e.g., example exploratory analysis scripts, data pipelines, simulation codes, numerical solvers, core community libraries, and research infrastructure) and study current verification practice in each via document analysis, repository mining, and structured interviews with practitioners. Output: an evidence base characterising what verification currently looks like per category, where it is failing under AI assistance, and where the gaps are most acute. Explicitly does not produce recommendations; it produces the empirical foundation that recommendations would need.

Size of task: Medium-large. ~9–12 FTE-months across a mixed-methods PI, an RA, and per-category fieldwork.

Readiness: Medium. Methodologically tractable; the conceptual framing is relatively clear. Dependencies: (1) a PI with mixed-methods experience and standing in the RSE community; (2) recruitment across the chosen categories; (3) ethics approval; (4) explicit choice of which existing taxonomy to anchor on.

Key stakeholders: RSE practitioners across the studied categories; authors of existing research-software taxonomies; empirical SE researchers; the ReSA community as readership; funders interested in research software quality.

Venues / opportunities: Publication at an empirical SE venue plus an RSE-community venue; data and instruments published openly; presentation at future RSE conferences; coordination with taxonomy authors to feed findings back into the categorisation work.

Existing commitments / momentum: Builds on existing taxonomy literature rather than starting from scratch. No WG-level commitments yet confirmed.

4G: Verification and validation of scientific software that contains AI components at runtime

Investigate the V&V problem for research software that includes AI components in the running pipeline (e.g., tool-calling agents, ML-based model surrogates and emulators, data-driven components substituting for expensive physical models). The methodological challenges are distinct from those of LLM-generated code: the system is stochastic, the AI component may be a closed model that updates without notice, and the component often substitutes for something the scientist explicitly does not want to verify by inspection (the whole point of a surrogate is that it replaces something costly). Likely a programme combining (a) a survey across domains where this pattern is now common (climate, chemistry, physics, astronomy), (b) development and evaluation of differential-testing and regression-testing approaches that work across model updates, and (c) connection to the broader ML-in-production literature.

Size of task: Large. ~12–18 FTE-months across a scoping phase plus 2–3 follow-on studies; structured as a programme rather than a single grant.

Readiness: Low–Medium. Framing is clear and the use cases are growing rapidly.

Dependencies: (1) a PI or steering group spanning empirical SE, ML evaluation, and at least one domain where surrogates are already in scientific use; (2) initial scoping work to identify the most tractable subset of the problem; (3) coordination with the ML-in-production research community where the analogous industrial problem is partially understood.

Key stakeholders: Domains where ML surrogates and emulators are now embedded in scientific pipelines (climate, structural biology, chemistry, astronomy); empirical software engineering researchers; the ML evaluation community; researchers working on the maintenance and provenance of pipelines that depend on third-party models.

Venues / opportunities: Initial scoping workshop at RSE or SE conferences (e.g., Super Computing) or co-located with a relevant machine learning venue; subsequent studies published at empirical SE and ML evaluation venues; coordinated funding call across funders with both AI-safety and research-infrastructure interests.

Existing commitments / momentum: Christian Kästner's *Machine Learning in Production* provides a substantial methodological starting point from the industrial side. The WG itself flagged surrogate testing and regression testing under model updates as concrete entry points. No WG-level commitments yet confirmed.

4H: Behavioural verification methods for research software pipelines

Develop and empirically evaluate methods for verifying research software at the level of behaviour rather than implementation, thereby addressing the situation where LLMs make code cheap, code volumes unmanageable, and line-by-line review increasingly impractical.

Concretely: (a) characterise what behavioural verification means for representative scientific pipelines across 2–3 domains, (b) develop and test specific approaches such as agent-driven synthetic data generation for pipeline stress-testing, property-based testing for scientific invariants, and metamorphic testing where direct oracles are unavailable, and (c) evaluate whether these methods catch the failure modes that line-by-line review would have caught, and whether they catch failure modes that line-by-line review would have missed.

Size of task: Medium-large. ~9–12 FTE-months across a methods-focused PI and an RA, plus per-domain pilot work.

Readiness: Medium. Several of the underlying techniques (property-based testing, metamorphic testing, synthetic data generation) are established in industrial SE; the contribution is their adaptation, evaluation, and adoption in scientific pipeline contexts. Dependencies: (1) a PI with footing in software testing research and access to pipeline-rich domains; (2) recruitment of 2–3 pipelines for empirical work; (3) ethics approval where pipelines process human-subjects data.

Key stakeholders: Empirical software engineering researchers working on testing methods; RSE teams maintaining data pipelines; domain scientists who would be the eventual users of behavioural verification methods; reproducibility researchers.

Venues / opportunities: Publication at empirical software engineering venues (ICSE, FSE, EMSE) plus an RSE-community venue; open release of methods, instruments, and benchmark pipelines; presentation at future RSE conferences.

Existing commitments / momentum: Property-based and metamorphic testing have established literatures in industrial software engineering that this work would adapt rather than originate. The WG itself called out agent-driven synthetic data generation for pipeline behaviour assessment as a specific tractable starting point. No WG-level commitments yet confirmed

WG5: Definition of RSE

5.1 Pilots

5A: Visual aid to describe changing role of RSE in the context of GenAI

Size of task: Small

Readiness: In progress - see the resulting blog post, [Research Software Engineers in the Age of GenAI: Same Value, Changing Practice](#) by Stephan Druskat et al.

Key Stakeholders: RSE community initially, then larger research software community overall

Venues / opportunities: “RSE value proposition doesn’t change; clearly articulate what RSEs provide that AI cannot” & RSE event talk(s)

5B: Propose/Organize workshop(s) that brings together practitioners to share success/failures/learnings of using AI in research software

- Ideally would allow participants to include latest work, not just based on what they submitted (far enough in advance to use the acceptance to be able to attend)
- Idea would be to keep it low-effort for RSEs
- Benefits
 - Would give the participants credit / a reason to attend the event
 - Would help the larger community understand what works and what doesn’t
 - Would destigmatize talking about using AI by sharing real experiences
- Work to do
 - Record presentations
 - Write-up summaries / lessons learned / best practices?

- Collection of agent skills / [AGENT.md](#) / tools to safely use agents?
- Dissemination
 - Publish agent work in the new Journal of Agent Skills?
 - Share summaries with institutions that hire/support RSEs
 - Publish summary paper of summaries?

Size of task: Medium

Readiness: High. Needs more detail but the idea is essentially ready for submission to RSECon 2026.

Venues / opportunities:

- Could be at RSECon and/or equivalent events
- Could be virtual workshop(s) as well

Key Stakeholders: RSEs and people/organisations who interact with them

Venues / opportunities:

- RSECon or another conference, something that RSEs would want to attend
- Would this fit? <https://rsecon26.society-rse.org/calls/interactive-sessions/> Seems 'workshop' is more a tutorial at RSECon (or BoF?)
- Alternative is to try to fit this in with the RSE for HPC workshop at SC26

5.2 Studies

5C: Case study of the AI practices and how they are changing for researchers, RSEs, and SEs, across industries and fields

- Usage patterns of AI across different roles in academia
- Attitudes/adoption rates
- Predictions about change in own adoption
- Helps determine what training is needed for RSEs, and what RSEs need to learn, in order to continue to be effective RSEs, operating in a space where they can take SE lessons and apply them to research beyond what a researcher can do themselves
- What are software skills, their relative importance, and the frequency of these skills used by all three groups
- What is the irreducible human expertise that RSEs provide that genAI cannot?

Size of task: Large

Readiness: Low

Key Stakeholders:

Venues / opportunities:

5D: Demonstrate that RSE + AI is more effective for research software than R + AI (or SE + AI)

- Mine repos that are of research software; determine who did the work; determine the impact of the software
- Are researchers who work with RSEs more successful in their careers than those who don't?
- Could do through interviews / ethnographic
- A similar/related Schmidt-funded study underway (CMU & UW) - might mean this isn't needed, or might be an input into this

Size of task: Large

Readiness: Low

Key Stakeholders:

Venues / opportunities:

WG6: Identifying and Developing Necessary Training

6.1 Pilots

6A: Community of Practice for teaching research software with AI

- Educators sharing experience and findings on what they're trying and what's working and what isn't
- Some type of platform to share lesson plans, materials, case studies,
- Asynchronous communication opportunities
- Possibly virtual calls
- How to share out beyond the community? (email newsletter below as well)

Size of task: Medium

Readiness: In progress. The Carpentries will begin hosting monthly Community of Practice meetings in June, discussing the interface of genAI and teaching. Calls will combine invited presentations and open community discussion to facilitate exchange of ideas and experience reports between educators. A [mailing list](#) has been established to share announcements and asynchronous community discussion to complement the community calls.

Key stakeholders:

- [Skills and Training for Research Software Forum \(STaRS\)](#)
- Carpentries communities
- US Department of Energy workforce development group under the umbrella of CASS (Consortium for Advancement of Scientific Software) <https://cass.community/>
- Later: Chartered institutes - accreditation bodies - IEEE, etc. -

Venues / opportunities: Looking for something that bridges across specific organizations

- [Skills and Training for Research Software Forum \(STaRS\)](#)
- Carpentries communities

Challenges: Recognition of different learning communities and type of learners

Impact:

- Give community to people who are teaching
- Help trainers get through the transition to incorporating and teaching AI tools
- Impact on researchers creating their own software and who work with RSEs
- Funding needed for:
 - Dedicated funding for community calls would enable scheduling events at a higher frequency and compensating presenters.
 - Money to buy people's time to develop new materials and lead the community;
 - Maybe for hosting a platform;
 - Funding for a dedicated in-person workshop on teaching with AI
 - Travel funding for instructors to visit and observe each other and participate in different training opportunities

6B: Email newsletter sharing practices, studies on teaching

Newsletter for educators, collating and commentating on new developments in the space

- What's needed: someone/some group needs to make it happen regularly; mechanism for for community contributions; publicity of it to get the word

Size of task: Small

- Fund a person for a dedicated chunk of time to make sure this happens - proportion of someone's time - someone who is a practitioner or researcher or in the teaching community who can editorialize and evaluate content and create it

Readiness: High. Need to identify who will lead this and host this, then can get started - ReSA STaRS Forum could be an option

Key stakeholders:

Venues / opportunities: STaRS forum could potentially own, other newsletters could cross list and share materials

Impact: Facilitates uptake of good practices and sharing of evidence and materials; broader reach than the community of practice but also provide a forum for dissemination of what the community discusses

6.2 Studies

6C: Qualitative meta analysis/systematic review article on current practices and assessment methods

- Scope: Specific focus on research software
- gather what evidence exists at this point

Size of task: Medium

- Fund a researcher to do the study and produce the article - 1 person - 1 year - 1 PI type project

Readiness: Medium

Key stakeholders:

Venues / opportunities:

Challenges: rapidly changing landscape

Impact:

- have a single summary to work from when looking for evidence based practice and gaps
- Grounding for community of practice and development of new materials
- How to move out of guesses, vibes
- Has potential to be repeated in the future as things change

6D: Understand what needs to be taught for being productive in teams while adopting genAI in their workflow using existing data

Science teams have different degrees of adoption of AI, and even within the teams people do it differently. [Next-Generation Ecosystems for Scientific Computing](#) (NGESC) has conducted a survey that asked several questions about infusion of AI in their work. It is possible that some queries can be answered from the responses already gathered. Set up a working group to explore the data and identify insights that might be extracted from it.

Size of task: Small

- 2-3 people to do analysis and report out
- can happen without funding

Readiness: High. Responses have already been collected and collated. We need to figure out what to ask. Could also be interesting to compare to responses to the International RSE Survey.

Key stakeholders:

- All medium to large scientific software developing teams
- The people who collected the data: will need to consent to its use + be engaged in the discussion

Venues / opportunities: NA

Challenges: formulating queries

WG7: Playbook for Managers and OSS Leaders

7.1 Pilots

7A: RSE Managers' AI Adoption Playbook

Deliver a community-authored, openly licensed playbook for RSE team leaders and managers navigating AI adoption within their teams. Intended to help managers support their teams through this transition effectively. Key milestones may include consultation with RSEs on scope and content, road-mapping and managing and assembling contributions e.g. on GitHub or another open collaboration platform.

Size of task: Medium-large: Writing phase ~8-12 months; ~10 FTE-months core effort;

Readiness: Medium-High. *Key dependencies:* establishment of an “Organising / Editorial Team”, funding to compensate authors for their written submissions.

Key stakeholders: RSE team leads, RSE Managers. US-RSE, Society of RSE, ReSA.

Venues / opportunities: RSE Society Slack to recruit contributors and editors; ADSA/US-RSE Career Guidebook contributors as a potential co-production partner.

Existing commitments / momentum: Commitment from an RSE leader. No other WG-level commitments yet confirmed

7B: OSS AI Adoption Playbook: guidance for open-source project leaders managing AI-era contributions

Coordinate with OSS communities to scope and then write and publish a companion guide for OSS project leaders on AI era challenges. Three challenges identified in the workshop were: (1) handling AI-generated contributions, including PR policies; (2) managing contribution quality

versus volume; (3) onboarding a distributed and diverse contributor and maintainer community into new standards and workflows.

Size of task: Medium. Writing phase ~8-12 months; ~10 FTE-months core effort;

Readiness: Low-Medium. Coordination with OSS governance communities needed to define scope. Communication with RSE playbook team needed to avoid duplication.

Key stakeholders: OSS project maintainers and leaders; contributors to large research software projects; Open Source Initiative, OpenSSF.

Venues / opportunities: OpenSSF Working Groups and FOSDEM for early scoping discussions with OSS governance communities;

Existing commitments / momentum: No WG-level commitments yet confirmed.

7.2 Training

7C: Psychologically safe AI adoption: resources for RSE managers

Develop and pilot with RSE Managers, resources covering psychologically safe AI skill transition. Content may include how to handle conscientious objectors and support team members experiencing craft-identity grieving (the loss of professional identity tied to skills being displaced by AI). This training addresses the human dimensions of AI adoption.

Size of task: Medium. ~4-8 FTE-months. Could begin as a short guide or facilitation toolkit and expand iteratively.

Readiness: Medium. Key dependencies: ideally requires input from someone with expertise in organisational change / psychological safety (i.e. an academic collaborator); an organising team.

Key stakeholders: RSE team leads, RSE Managers. US-RSE, Society of RSE, [ConveRSE](#) (Let's Talk about Metal Health [in RSE]) (This group was not represented at this workshop but would be a natural collaborator).

Venues / opportunities: RSE Society Slack to recruit contributors and editors;

Existing commitments / momentum: [ConveRSE](#) (Let's Talk about Metal Health [in RSE]) - not yet approached may be a potential production partner.

7D: Upskilling materials for RSE managers: onboarding to the LLM era

Write and publish peer-authored onboarding materials to help RSE managers upskill on current LLM capabilities and practical team-level AI integration. Materials can integrate into the playbook or be released as a standalone resource e.g. as summary articles in a suitable journal venue.

Size of task: Small-medium. ~3-5 FTE-months for a first version; maintained as a living document with community contributions.

Readiness: Medium. Content tractable now; needs a small coordinating team..

Key stakeholders: RSE group leads new to AI tooling; experienced RSEs contributing use cases; US-RSE, Society of RSE.

Venues / opportunities: RSE Society Slack to recruit peer authors and reviewers.

Existing commitments / momentum: No WG-level commitments yet confirmed; This has significant overlap with an existing [DisCouRSE project](#) by Kamilla Kopec-harding (confirmed) which has committed to provide practical guidance on responsible AI-assisted development for technical leaders (these DisCouRSE guides could provide an initial first draft for these on-boarding materials which could be extended and maintained in this project).

7E: Low-hype LLM training: peer-led workshops for RSEs on modern AI capabilities

Design and run 'from us, to us' style training or meetings for RSEs on modern LLM capabilities, and build a community-maintained collection of use cases and ways of adopting LLM usage in research software workflows. Sessions can use the 'projector-side chat' format - a practitioner demos on-stage while a peer interviewer zooms from 'what's that specific widget?' to 'what does this all mean for us?', making sessions accessible to non-technical attendees as well as practitioners. Optionally, seek ring-fenced funding for cross-institutional site visits (talks and hackathons); the CAKE placement scheme (<https://www.cake.ac.uk/about/placements/>) was identified as a potentially relevant funding call that could be used for this purpose if separate funding for site visits cannot be identified.

Size of task: Small for core workshops (~2-3 FTE-months to develop); Medium if site visit funding pursued.

Readiness: High for workshops (community expertise available now). Medium for site visits (depends on identifying a sponsor or relevant funding call and then support to manage the funds).

Key stakeholders: RSE practitioners; RSE group leads; US-RSE, Society of RSE; potential funders for the site visits component.

Venues / opportunities: RSE Society Slack to coordinate session organisers and use-case contributors; BoF or workshop slot at RSECon26 or US-RSE26 (<https://us-rse.org/usrse26/participate/>)

Existing commitments / momentum: No WG-level commitments yet.

7.3 Studies

7F: Delphi study: challenges and experiences of RSE managers navigating AI adoption

Recruit a diverse panel of RSE managers and run a structured Delphi study on the challenges and experiences of managers as they grapple with AI adoption, facilitating iterative rounds to

build consensus. Produce synthetic vignettes reflecting the key challenges, directly usable for playbook development and training.

A methodological variant of this study might use an AI-assisted conversation e.g. a Claude / Codex skill to structure qualitative data collection from the RSE managers (AI-assisted Delphi).

Size of task: Medium. ~4-6 FTE-months (main Delphi study: design, 2-3 rounds, analysis, vignette writing) Requires a Delphi-experienced facilitator / someone willing to upskill on this research method.

Readiness: Medium. Well-established methodology; needs 15-30 manager panellists and a Delphi-experienced/ willing PI. Template variant can start immediately as a prompt-engineering task.

Key stakeholders: RSE managers as panellists; social science or education researchers as collaborators.

Venues / opportunities: RSE Society Slack to coordinate session organisers and use-case contributors; BoF or workshop slot at RSECon26 or US-RSE26 (<https://us-rse.org/usrse26/participate/>)

Existing commitments / momentum: identified as core input to playbook content. AI assisted approach inspired by <https://www.aiforeducation.io/prompts/coaching-conversation-framework>. Kamilla Kopec-Harding (confirmed) has volunteered to be involved in this.

WG8: Making GenAI Accessible to All

8.1 Pilots

8A: Communications plan and community management for engaging diverse targeted groups in AI in research (software/computing) discussions

This would aim to support public discourse around access to GenAI for research software with commission/incentives for contribution.

Size of task: Medium

Readiness: Low. Needs a UX expert

Key stakeholders: National RSE associations for Chile, Africa, Asia, plus SSI, DEI WG in SocRSE and USRSE; and broader groups such as CURIOS, HELIOS, Open Forum for AI, or other academic groups that engage in some fashion with research software.

Venues / opportunities:

- Invited blog posts (or similar) from 4-6 individuals along the axes
 - A podcast season (e.g. on something like [SustainOSS](#)).
-

8B: Engaging a selection of underrepresented knowledge axes through workshops, and/or through funding / incubators

- Bringing together the people who are already doing this work in other areas for two-way / multi-way exchange
- Funding for initial workshop(s) in this area
- E.g. through conference / workshop, funding / incubator

Size of task: Large

Readiness: Low

Key stakeholders:

- E.g. copyrights lawyers, ethics/philosophy

Venues/opportunities: Go where the people can go / be

8.2 Training

8C: Providing playbooks for equitable AI in research advocacy

Size of task: Large (based on experience from HiddenREF)

Readiness: Low

Key stakeholders:

- RS people talking to the senior leadership / policymakers
- Policy officers advising senior leadership / policymakers

Venues/opportunities:

- An example might be: Targeting a group of researchers working on governmental and institutional policy with [OpenTechResearch](#), for instance. A new [Digital Infrastructure Insights Fund](#), but for RS-AI.
-

8.3 Studies

8D: Post-workshop questions on demographic of participants and who should have been here

Size of task: Small

Readiness: Only requires agreement on questions

Key stakeholders: Workshop attendees

Venues/opportunities: Post-workshop survey

8E: How research software practitioners from varied knowledge axes (e.g. different domains) interface with AI policy/norms

- Understand how we can make it normalised that reflexivity statements need to incorporate LLMs and how you are addressing marginalization
- Where Ethics Boards are not normalized, provide framework for local development of such a board

Size of task: Medium

Readiness: Low. This should place in conjunction with 8C

Key stakeholders: To be decided in conjunction with 8C

Venues / opportunities: Pilot through an RSE adjacent journal and/or other journals we can influence

8F: Longitudinal study identifying how LLM-using projects onboard marginalised groups

- Study the ways that projects understand and reflect on how they onboard contributors from marginalised groups through their usage of LLM tools
- Pilot: Create ways to signal “safety signals” for marginalised contributors. Build template e.g. for effectively onboarding new marginalised contributors [CONTRIBUTING.md](#) with buy-in from maintainers
 - Work with a set of research projects to trial and give feedback

Size of task: Large

Readiness: Medium. Some substantial pre-work to do study design, potentially relies on Pilot 3A

Key stakeholders: *Which people or groups should be included?*

- Need to identify suitable projects, potentially relies on Pilot 3A
- Identify a (small) team that is dedicated to planning and executing this study

Venues / opportunities: Opportunities to present this work at RSE conferences, domain conferences, and possibly in academic journal(s)

8H: State of the Field paper on where specifically are the biases in current infrastructure in research software

Size of task: Large

Readiness: Medium. Some substantial pre-work to do study design

Key stakeholders: Need to identify a small team dedicated to planning and executing the study

Venues / opportunities:

- Publish in an academic journal focused in the RSE/AI/Computational Research space
- *Publish in informal venues such as RSE blogs*
- Opportunities to present this work at RSE conferences, domain conferences, and possibly in academic journal(s)

WG9: Collaboration: Working Together, Not Just with AI

9.1 Pilots

9A: AI-assisted requirements gathering ("PRD skill") for research software collaborations

Build and pilot an AI tool that walks researcher–RSE pairs through a structured product requirement document at project kick-off. It asks persona-specific questions (domain questions for the researcher, technical/stack questions for the RSE, deployment questions for devops) designed to surface what "good" looks like, i.e., success metrics, constraints, assumptions, scope. All collected before implementation starts. Pilot with 2–3 real incoming RSE engagements and measure whether it reduces downstream scope churn.

Size of task: Medium. ~3–6 FTE-months across a prompt/system-design lead plus light evaluation; additional time contributed in-kind by pilot-site RSE groups.

Readiness: Medium. Underlying work is largely prompt/context/skill engineering, not model research. Key dependencies: (1) 2–3 RSE groups willing to route new engagements through the tool and share outcomes; (2) an agreed evaluation design so results are interpretable; (3) a working definition of "PRD" for research software, which is probably less well established than in industry.

Key stakeholders: RSE group leads and their researcher collaborators; university RSE service teams; the ReSA community; funders interested in research software effectiveness.

Venues / opportunities: Embed pilot in 2–3 existing RSE groups; present at RSECon26 (BoF or talk); open-source the prompts/tool in a public GitHub repo; short methods write-up somewhere public.

Existing commitments / momentum: Natural alignment with the Schmidt Sciences [VISS](#) program – Arfon Smith (arfon@schmidtsciences.org, confirmed) on spec-driven development and agentic workflows, which is a potential collaborator and reference point. No WG-level commitments yet confirmed.

9B: Cross-domain translation tool for RSE "cold starts"

Build and evaluate a tool that ingests a research group's recent papers, codebases, and data descriptions and produces a technical briefing oriented toward an incoming RSE. This could cover things such as data formats, computational constraints, existing tooling, and implicit domain assumptions. Aim: compress the painful ramp-up period when an RSE joins a new group. Potentially evaluate via time-to-first-useful-contribution and onboarding-RSE survey.

Size of task: Small-medium. ~2–4 FTE-months across development, pilot, and light evaluation.

Readiness: High. Primarily a context-assembly and prompt engineering problem. The main uncertainty is evaluation design, not feasibility. Dependencies: (1) 1–2 RSE groups willing to use it with incoming collaborators; (2) consent/access to group-level materials; (3) a simple evaluation instrument.

Key stakeholders: RSE group leads regularly onboarding to new collaborations; RSEs themselves; researchers who host RSE collaborators; university-hosted RSE teams.

Venues / opportunities: Open-source release in a public GitHub repo; demo at future RSE conference; short experience report via a ReSA channel.

Existing commitments / momentum: Opportunity was widely recognised by WG participants; informal interest likely available to recruit pilot sites. No named commitments yet.

9C: AI-drafted decision and assumption logs for research software projects

Prototype a tool that monitors team communications (issue tracker, commit messages, selected chat channels) and drafts a running log of project decisions and assumptions. In the spirit of Architecture Decision Records (ADRs), these would be generated by the AI for humans to review, correct, and retain. The hypothesis is that the AI doesn't need to be right; it needs to produce a draft that's faster to edit than to write from scratch. Pilot with 2–3 teams; measure adoption, perceived usefulness, and downstream use for onboarding and reproducibility.

Size of task: Medium. ~4–6 FTE-months across development, pilot integration, and evaluation.

Readiness: Medium. Underlying AI work is tractable (extraction + summarisation).

Dependencies: (1) agreement from pilot teams on which communication channels can be ingested; (2) privacy/consent handling; (3) a formative evaluation design, with a longer study possible later.

Key stakeholders: RSEs and research teams maintaining long-lived software; reproducibility and research-software-sustainability communities; practitioners who are working at a level where the ADR paradigm makes sense to them.

Venues / opportunities: Open-source prototype in a public GitHub repo; demo/BoF at RSECon26; short experience paper at a reproducibility or RSE venue; potential conversation with ReSA working groups on software sustainability.

Existing commitments / momentum: Public ADR template repositories (e.g. the widely used [joelparkerhenderson/architecture-decision-record](https://github.com/joelparkerhenderson/architecture-decision-record) on GitHub) provide prior art and a starting template. No WG-level commitments yet.

9.2 Studies

9D: SPACE-framework study of research teams adopting AI collaboration tools

Run a mixed-methods study using the SPACE framework (Satisfaction, Performance, Activity, Communication, Efficiency) to measure what changes when research teams adopt AI collaboration tools such as coding agents, meeting summarisers, PR reviewers, etc. Combine a diary study with lightweight instrumentation or a panel survey across a cohort of teams over 6+ months. Output is evidence on human-factors effects (satisfaction, cross-member communication, collaboration quality), not just code output.

Size of task: Medium-large. ~9–12 FTE-months total, split across a mixed-methods lead and a research assistant.

Readiness: Medium. SPACE is an established framework, so methodological scaffolding exists.

Dependencies: (1) cohort of 6–12 research teams with comparable maturity willing to be observed longitudinally; (2) IRB/ethics approval for a multi-site behavioural study; (3) a PI with empirical software engineering experience connected to the RSE community.

Key stakeholders: Empirical software engineering researchers; RSE group leads willing to have their teams participate; the broader RSE community as readership; meta-science / research-on-research funders.

Venues / opportunities: Publication in an empirical SE venue (EMSE, ICSE SEIP) plus an RSE-community venue; protocol and instruments published openly for replication; present at RSE conferences or applied software engineering venues.

Existing commitments / momentum: Potential adjacent work studying Schmidt Sciences' [VISS](#) program – Arfon Smith (arfon@schmidtsciences.org, confirmed) engagements provides complementary observational data on a different cohort. No direct WG commitments yet.

9E: Empirical study: does AI mediation change the epistemic quality of research collaborations?

Design and run a study of how AI mediation changes research outcomes, not just speed or satisfaction. Look at reference diversity, cross-domain transfer, the presence or absence of productive disagreement, and whether AI-mediated teams surface or smooth over constructive friction. Likely a mixed-methods design combining ethnographic observation of a small number of teams with a broader quantitative component.

Size of task: Large. ~12–18 FTE-months total, split across a mixed-methods PI and a postdoc or research assistant, plus fieldwork time.

Readiness: Low–Medium. Framing is clear, but the measurement piece is hard as “epistemic quality” is not a solved problem. Dependencies: (1) a PI with footing in both science-of-science/STS and software engineering research; (2) research groups willing to be observed longitudinally; (3) upstream methods work to define what epistemic-quality signals can actually be measured.

Key stakeholders: Science-of-science and STS researchers; empirical software engineering researchers; the RSE community as study setting; meta-science funders.

Venues / opportunities: Funding via an existing meta-science / science-of-science programme; publication in STS and RSE venues; pre-registration on OSF; a methods-development BoF workshop at a future RSE conference.

Existing commitments / momentum: Aligns with a broader workshop interest in meta-science studies of collaboration changes. Therefore, it is worth coordinating with adjacent working groups rather than running in isolation. No direct commitments yet.